

THANK GOD PROJECT

CAMPAIGN PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT FOR URBAN-STRESS THERAPY

Anggia Widhi Purbowati,
Bandung Institute of Technology, Industrial Design Department.
anggia.widhi@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Urban stress has already become a big problem for the urban society itself and influenced their daily activities. However, such problem can be reduced by changing the people's behavior. Recent researches indicate that a product can change human behavior. Therefore, the development of a product concept which can change human behavior and mind can reduce urban stress. This project aims at giving a stress therapy product for urban society with an interactive and fun way yet has essential effect. The developed product remains an experimental product tested or used in a small scale.

Keywords: urban society, campaign product, mild stress therapy, grateful, behavioral design.

BACKGROUND

Urban life in big cities often creates pressure (stress) to its society. There are certainly many factors of stress. All demands of urban living and society activities can increase the brain work and lead to stress.

Mental health disorder case in urban areas, especially in Indonesia, has been increased. Approximately 20 - 30 percent of Indonesian society suffers mental health disorders, ranging from mild to severe mental health disorders. Out of the said percentage, approximately 2 - 3 percent of society suffers more severe mental disorders such as chronic insanity and schizophrenia, while the rest suffers less severe mental health disorders (Cecep (2009). forumkami.net. February 2012).

Mild stress should be relieved immediately. If it is not conducted, it will lead to more severe psychiatric problem causing schizophrenia. Out of many methods for relieving stress, the methods which can decrease the brain work are meditation and relaxation. Being grateful is one of the basic forms of mind meditation. The repetition of gratitude by the urban society can avoid stress which is derived from their various activities.

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Basically, the products designed must have a high frequency of interaction with the users and can be used by all parts of society. The development of campaign product conducted is intended to help urban society in creating behavior having positive influence on them. In this case, the behavior created is grateful behavior.

Figure 1 Thank God Project Logo

There are two types of design formation, namely individual formation in the form of stationery and

software for mobile phones, and general formation in the form of interactive public facilities.

STATIONERY PRODUCTS

Stamp

The first product development is a stamp which reads "Thank God ..." By using such stamp, the users can apply it by putting a stamp on any paper medium and be grateful for anything.

Figure 2 The "Thank God..." Stamp

This product has been tested on some people. It is applied mostly on their diary or schedule book and put on their important dates or days. In addition, they also give such stamp on their important documents, such as approved report drafts or some memorable photos.

Calendar

The users of this product must write the words of gratitude on a paper which is then affixed to the calendar every day. When the paper has been affixed to all days on the calendar, the paper will form a shape with interesting color. This new product was already tested on the author. This product can help to capture the traces of happiness felt every day. By only looking back at the calendar of the previous months, the user can recall the wonderful memories and smile.

Figure 3 The "Thank God..." Calendar

The formation of system similar to those attached on the calendar can also be used as a participatory design. It involves many people as its users who write the words of gratitude on the paper. Subsequently, the collection of such papers is attached on a field forming a particular shape.

Figure 4 The "Thank God..." Participatory Design that involved about 160 college students

Software

Nowadays, urban society is very close to the activities in their mobile phone. Therefore, the design development through mobile phone is one of the potential alternatives. The software scenario and system are as follows: in the beginning, the software shows the initial display which simply reads "Thank God ...", then the user writes the words of gratitude in the initial display. Following the writing of such words, the words will appear continuously as a screensaver or wallpaper or moving text on the mobile phone.

Figure 5 The "Thank God..." Trial Software

However, the writing will disappear after 24 hours and will be return as the initial display and the user must write new words to reactivate it.

Interactive Public Facility

The type of public facility product is also potential to be developed since the target of this campaign is the general public. The concept of public facility design itself is to give a space which provides different experience to the society with its surrounding environment when using this product. By using an interactive and playful system, the society will be able to 'play' with this product and foster interaction between the users of such product; while the interaction or communication is also one of the types of therapy which can relieve mild stress.

Public facilities may also become a means to share a sense of gratitude since the software developed will be able to interact with the public facilities. The words which appear on the LED display in such public facility will make other positive stimulus for the society. The scenario for interactive system on public facilities is as follows: If there are people walking under the product,

the light will illuminate and the voice will sound according to the position of the person. Subsequently, if there is another person entering the space, the voice will sound alternately while the color of light will converge at the top and do likewise.

However, if there are many people at one point, the light emitted from such point will be brighter and the people will hear more sound. While they are entertained by the interactive system on the product, their brains were also entertained by the stimulus of light and sound waves produced.

While for the people passing under the products and carrying mobile phone with the said software which contains the gratitude text, the text on their mobile phone will be sent to the product and appear on the LED screen for a few days. The more software users come to such point, the more writing appears on the LED screen. The more words of gratitude appear on the screen, the more positive stimulus is obtained by the society.

Figure 6 Interactive public facility design rendering and product scenario

The product is planned to be placed in public places frequently visited by the urban society such as city parks or open spaces in the shopping centers (malls). However, the design of public facility is still in the design concept phase.

CONCLUSION

By the development of this 'thank god' campaign product design, it is expected that it can provide a positive impact for the change of behavior and mind set of urban society. By the emergence of positive change in the mind set of society, stress faced by the urban society can be reduced. It is expected that the small change made by each individual can be a bigger change for the environment.

REFERENCES

Adel. (February 2012). 17. *Topik Bulan Ini – Gangguan Jiwa*. http://mitrapedulicenter.multiply.com/journal/item/2/17._Topik_Bulan

Ini-_Gangguan_Jiwa

Anneke. (7 November 2011). *Discussion about Urban Stress in Bandung*. Interview. Santo Boromeus Hospital.

Cecep. (February 2012). *Gangguan Jiwa Hantui 30 Persen Penduduk Indonesia*. <http://www.forumkami.net/kesehatan/23306-gangguan-jiwa-hantui-30-penduduk-indonesia.html>

Horne, Steven H. (October 2011). *Stress Relief Secret #4: Be Thankful for Your Problems*. <http://www.organicauthority.com/health/health/stress-relief-secret-4-be-thankful-for-your-problems.html>

Lederbogen, Florian, et al. (October 2011). *City living and urban upbringing affect neural social stress processing in humans*. <http://www.nature.com/nature/journal/v474/n7352/full/nature10190.html>

Petersen, Marianne Graves, Ole Sejer Iversen, dan Peter Gall Krogh. (October 2011). *Aesthetic Interaction - A Pragmatist's Aesthetic of Interactive Systems*. <http://www.cse.chalmers.se/research/group/idc/ituniv/kurser/06/idpr oj/p269-petersen.pdf>

Ross, Philip R. dan Stephan A. G. Wensveen. (2010). *Designing Behavior in Interaction: Using Aesthetic Experience as a Mechanism for Design*. International Journal of Design. Vol 4, no 2. 3-13.

Siregar, Chairil. (8 November 2011). *Discussion about Bandung Urban Society Characteristic*. Interview. Institut Teknologi Bandung.

Smith, Melinda, Robert Segal, and Jeanne Segal. (February 2012). *Understanding Stress*. http://helpguide.org/mental/stress_signs.htm